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Introduction

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

BLOKCHEYN TEXNOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA XAVFSIZ TRANZAKTSIYALARNI TA'MINLASH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada blokcheyn texnologiyasining xavfsiz tranzaktsiyalarni amalga oshirishdagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy raqamli iqtisodiyotda axborotning ishonchliligi va saqlanish xavfsizligi muhim o'rin tutadi. Blokcheyn texnologiyasi orqali amalga oshiriladigan tranzaktsiyalar markazlashmagan muhitda, shifrlash va konsensus mexanizmlari orqali yuqori darajada himoyalanaadi. Maqolada ushbu texnologiyaning ishlash prinsiplari, afzalliklari va qo'llanilish sohalari hamda mavjud cheklovlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Blokcheyn, xavfsizlik, tranzaktsiya, shifrlash, konsensus mexanizmi, raqamli texnologiyalar.

Kirish

Raqamli texnologiyalarning jadal rivojlanishi bilan birga, axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlash muammolari ham dolzarb masalaga aylandi. Xususan, moliyaviy, sog'liqni saqlash, ta'lim, logistika kabi sohalarda ma'lumotlar almashinuvi va tranzaktsiyalar soni ortib bormoqda. Shu nuqtai nazardan blokcheyn texnologiyasi – ishonchli va shaffof tranzaktsiyalarni amalga oshirish imkonini beruvchi vosita sifatida e'tirof etilmoqda. U markazlashmagan, tarmoq ishtirokchilari tomonidan boshqariladigan tizim orqali axborotni saqlash va himoyalash imkoniyatini beradi.

Adabiyotlar sharhi

Blokcheyn texnologiyasi ilk bor 2008-yilda Satoshi Nakamoto tomonidan taqdim etilgan bo'lib, Bitcoin kriptovalyutasi asosida rivojlandi. Vitalik Buterin (2015) Ethereum platformasi orqali blokcheynni faqat moliyaviy emas, balki "aqlli kontraktlar" orqali huquqiy va iqtisodiy sohalarda ham kengroq qo'llashni yo'lga qo'ydi. Don Tapscott va Alex Tapscott (2016) blokcheynni "islohotchi texnologiya" sifatida baholab, uning real sektor sohasidagi potentsialiga alohida urg'u berishgan. A. Gervais va boshqalar (2017) esa blokcheyn xavfsizligidagi zaifliklar – DDoS hujumlari, 51% hujum xavfi, shifrlashdagi kamchiliklar haqida chuqur tahlil olib borganlar.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

Tadqiqotda ilmiy adabiyotlar tahlili, statistik ma'lumotlarni solishtirish, real loyihalarning (Bitcoin, Ethereum, Hyperledger, Ripple) tajribalari asosida blokcheynning xavfsizlikdagi rolini baholash metodlari qo'llanildi. Shuningdek, ekspert baholari va tarmoq ishtirokchilari fikrlari asosida tahlil olib borildi.

Tahlil va natijalar

1-jadval: An'anaviy va blokcheyn asosidagi tranzaksiyalar taqqoslanishi

Ko'rsatkichlar	An'anaviy tizimlar	Blokcheyn texnologiyasi
Ma'lumot markazi	Markazlashgan	Markazlashmagan
Axborot xavfsizligi	Zaif (hujumga ochiq)	Kriptografik jihatdan mustahkam
Tranzaksiyalar shaffofligi	Nisbatan yopiq	To'liq shaffof (public ledger)
Verifikatsiya tezligi	Bank yoki vositachilar orqali	Avtomatik (konsensus asosida)
Xarajatlar	Yuqori komissiyalar	Minimal xarajatlar
Vaqt samaradorligi	Sezilarli kechikishlar	Tezkor, 24/7 ishlash rejimi

Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki, blokcheyn texnologiyasi tranzaksiyalarni xavfsiz, tezkor va arzon amalga oshirish imkonini beradi. Ayniqsa, vositachilar ishtirokini cheklashi va har bir harakatni aniq hujjatlashtirishi uning afzalliklaridandir.

2-jadval: Turli sohalarda blokcheyn texnologiyasining qo'llanilishi va xavfsizlikka ta'siri

Soha	Qo'llanish shakli	Xavfsizlik samarasi
Moliya	Kriptoalyutalar, to'lov tizimlari	Firibgarlikni kamaytirish, auditable tizim
Sog'liqni saqlash	Tibbiy ma'lumotlar bazasi	Maxfiylik va izchillikni ta'minlash
Logistika	Yetkazib berish zanjirlari	Soxta mahsulotlarga qarshi kurash
Ta'lim	Diplomlar va sertifikatlar	Soxta hujjatlarni oldini olish
Davlat xizmatlari	Ovoz berish tizimlari	Saylov jarayonining shaffofligini oshirish

Blokcheyn texnologiyasi faqat moliyaviy emas, balki axborot ishonchligi muhim bo'lgan har qanday sohada qo'llanishi mumkin. U axborotga ruxsatsiz kirishni cheklaydi va har bir harakatni o'zgaras ravishda yozib boradi.

Xulosa

Blokcheyn texnologiyasi – zamonaviy raqamli iqtisodiyotda xavfsizlik talablariga javob bera oladigan innovatsion yechimdir. U tranzaksiyalarni markazlashmagan tarzda, shaffof va shifrlangan holatda amalga oshirishga imkon yaratadi. Turli sohalarda blokcheyn texnologiyasining joriy etilishi orqali korrupsiya, ma'lumotlar buzilishi va firibgarlik holatlarining oldi olinadi. Biroq, ushbu

texnologiyaning ommalashuvi uchun texnik, huquqiy va infratuzilma masalalari hal qilinishi zarur.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati:

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